

THE IMPORTANCE OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

This article investigates the role and the importance of using idiomatic expressions in English language. Idiomatic expressions are group of words with concrete meaning which can be unrelated to the meaning of individual words. They make our speech more sensitive and colourful. In fact, the structure of idioms can be wrong grammatically, but the precise meaning can be seen in this way. Moreover, it can be seen that learners compare the English idiomatic expression in equivalence Russian one (in mother tongue).

Key words: idiom, culture, meaningful, tradition, using in speech, authentic, communicative.

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An idiom is a phrase or saying that is commonly used in everyday English to express certain ideas or opinions. Understanding English idioms is important because they require a deeper familiarity of the English language to comprehend what someone means when they use them in conversation.

Idioms have their foundation in the fiber of social interaction, with some dating back over 3,000 years. All idioms, from the oldest to the most modern, owe their origins to the processes of human thinking and language development. They build personal experience, making even the oldest of them current in today's world. It is no surprise, then, that idioms are prevalent in everyday human speech. In practice, idioms are used in many languages to reflect the facts of daily life. Idioms are so common in ordinary conversation that Hoffman, referring to native English speakers, calculated their usage at 7,000 each week, however this has yet to be verified empirically. Nonetheless, the usage of idioms by members of a language group reflects the cultural spirit of the people who use them, independent of how frequently they are employed. Idioms get to be the reflection of people's worlds, their aspirations and anxieties, their lives and deaths, because they are rooted in their history, politics, sports, and culture. In other words, idioms form a part of the language's spiritual character. As a result, idiom education across the whole second language curriculum—from basic to higher levels of language instruction—gives second and foreign language learners an exceptional opportunity to evaluate target-language growth over time. While not all utterances formed become idioms, those that do can provide useful information about sociocultural contexts and the creative nature of human mind. Idioms change throughout time and space as language changes. In the

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culture of the people who speak a specific language, idioms have both textual and traditional figurative interpretations, as previously stated. The former can be determined using a combination of syntactic, and semantic analysis, but the latter can only be remembered from memory, if the literal meaning of the idiom has already been formed in the learner's vocabulary, or if it can be inferred from a literal analysis of the individual vocabulary that make up the idiom, combined with an imagery of the learner's prior knowledge and evaluation of the communicative context in which the literal meaning occurs. Being aware of how idioms are used in a specific group seems to be a vital first step toward idiomatic competency. The knowledge that ideas and thoughts can be presented in a number of ways is also significant. In our first language, we all excel at this.

To know idiomatic expressions is useful for both students and teachers. Perhaps, students should have previous knowledge about idioms, they have to improve communicative skills through idioms and know how to use in speech. Then, if teachers use more idiomatic expressions during lesson, students may have experience of using them. Inherently, interactive games and activities through using idioms may enrich usage of idioms. For instance, the task can be like "Find some idiomatic expressions and find equivalent of them in your own mother tongue. Then compare them". For example: "On cloud nine" is equal in Russian "на седьмом небе"

It is raining cats and dogs- льет как из ведра.

It means too much heavy rain.

A drop in the bucket- капля в море.

A very small quantity, especially one that is too small. For example, these tasks are just a drop in the bucket, others are difficult thousand more.

Very big-конца краю нет.

Something that no end.

A bag of bones-кожа да кости.

A very thin person or animal.

Some idioms are closely connected with the names of literal works. The song Night Owl was originally written by James Taylor. Of course, "night owl" is an idiom for someone who likes to stay out late (it's not a literal owl). However, most people don't realize that the idiom "night owl" actually originated with Shakespeare – it's a line from his Richard II.

Majority of idioms are unique in their grammatical structure. Some of their structures are wrong. For instance, to be broke is grammatically incorrect but it has the idiomatic meaning of to have no money. He is broke and can not go to the theatre.

To conclude, Idioms, proverbs and expressions in English are an important part of everyday English. They always appear in written and spoken English. Since idioms are not always literal, you need to be familiar with the meaning and usage of each language. This may seem like a lot of work, but learning idioms is fun, especially when you compare English idioms with idioms in your own language.

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